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Abstract

Deliverable 8.4 summarizes the outcomes of the activities of Task 8.6 “International dimension” in WP8. Task 8.6 intended to continue the networking activities promoted by the stream of Integrating Activity European projects carried out by the heritage science community. The aim of these actions, which were particularly intense in the forerunner project IPERION CH [1], is reinforcing and extending the international network of cooperation established in the last 20 years by the heritage science community, in view of the permanent establishment of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS ERIC). Unfortunately, international activities were severely impaired by the pandemic emergency to the point of being unfeasible. At the end of the pandemic, the global tensions and wars which arisen, and still are ongoing, made international cooperation activities and science diplomacy actions more difficult than in the past.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
ANTECIPA	<i>Associação Nacional de Pesquisa em Tecnologia e Ciência do Patrimônio</i>
E-RIHS	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Forum for Research Infrastructures
GCI	The Getty Conservation Institute
HS	Heritage Science
INAH	<i>Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia</i>
MCI	Museum Conservation Institute of the Smithsonian Institution
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RI	Research Infrastructure
SEM-EDS	Scanning Electron Microscopy – Energy Dispersive Spectroscopy
UFMG	<i>Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais</i>
UNAM	<i>Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México</i>
WP	Work Package

Narrative (technical) description

1. Introduction

This document, entitled “Final Report on International Activities”, is Deliverable 8.4 of the project IPERION HS and it has been elaborated in the framework of Task 8.6 “International Dimension” in WP8.

Task 8.6 was planned to reinforce and extend the relationships with initiatives, networks and institutions that were considered potential partners of the IPERION HS/E-RIHS global ecosystem. Unfortunately, most of the activities planned for Task 8.6 were severely impaired, to the point of being unfeasible. This happened due to the impact of the prolonged stop caused by the pandemic emergency, which prevented regular travelling for more than two years.

In the midst of all these very unfortunate and unpredictable events, the approval of the EU-LAC ResInfra project [4] proved to be a lucky turn also for the IPERION HS international cooperation activities. The ResInfra project aimed at building a bi-regional collaboration between European Union and the Latin America Caribbean countries, to prove the importance of Research Infrastructures for joint Research and Development activities. The project contained a pilot action for E-RIHS, centred on heritage science data interoperability, that was scheduled to be performed together with the Brazilian and Mexican E-RIHS Hubs, which are also partners of IPERION HS (UFMG and UNAM). The pilot led by E-RIHS aimed to strengthen the bi-regional cooperation between infrastructures operating in heritage science, by exploring solutions for achieving scientific data interoperability, thus laying the foundations for the construction of a common digital research environment based on the availability of heritage science FAIR data. With the start of ResInfra, it was decided to support the E-RIHS pilot action jointly with the IPERION HS project. This way we were able to reinforce both the pilot activities originally planned and the cooperation with the two American partners.

When the pandemic emergency finally ended, the slow return to normality in international travel and relationships was heavily disturbed by new political instabilities and war(s). These events made the return to normality international cooperation in the heritage science domain a very hard task. In some cases, the cooperation had to be interrupted: this happened with Russia, where good scientific and diplomatic contacts for E-RIHS were already opened. Even the interest of Ukraine towards E-RIHS, made concrete by a workshop organized in Odessa in December 2019, was interrupted by the events. These instabilities are still protracting to date, and they are still preventing smooth cooperation actions to be taken.

Finally, the start of E-RIHS IP, the implementation project for the E-RIHS ERIC, directed us to gradually shift the focus of international cooperation under the “permanent” label of E-RIHS, avoiding opening new cooperation paths under the IPEIRON HS project label, which will disappear with the end of the project and the establishment of the ERIC. That could have confused the potential new partners. The new actions of cooperation are now the subject of Task 6.3

“Strengthening E-RIHS cooperation on the EU scene and beyond” of the project E-RIHS IP, which is designing the international cooperation policies of the upcoming ERIC.

2. Actions planned but not performed

During the development of the IPERION HS project, several international initiatives were to be organized to connect, or to maintain the existing connection, with international partners showing high interest and commitment to take part in a future “Global E-RIHS”. The original focus was set to the American and Eurasian regions, due to the limited time and resources available. In particular, the Task planned to co-organize two international symposia:

- the “Pan-American Workshop on Heritage Science” at the Getty Conservation Institute in Los Angeles (US), involving all the major heritage science hubs in the two American continents;
- a joint workshop with the “Alliance for Science and Heritage along the Silk Road” in collaboration with prominent Chinese cultural institutions.

These (and other) initiatives were planned to showcase the Heritage Science community global dimension and to offer opportunities to HS researchers for international cooperation and mobility. The model of the E-RIHS research infrastructure (including e.g. TNA platforms, training modules, etc.) would have been promoted at the global level by dissemination of good practices and by success stories of already developed mirror initiatives, implemented internationally following to the IPERION/E-RIHS model of serving the heritage community. These international exchanges were also thought to enable the development of a Global research infrastructure for Heritage Science.

International cooperation activities and science diplomacy are fundamentally based on face-to-face meetings and thus they were severely impacted by the pandemic emergency. All the in-presence activities planned for the first two years of the project (2020 and 2021) were initially postponed, and among these the expected Pan-American Workshop on Heritage Science. The joint organization of this important workshop was agreed in December 2018 with the Director of GCI in Mexico City, during a bilateral meeting of IPERION CH. It was then introduced in the proposal of IPERION HS, with the possible timeline of holding the meeting in Los Angeles, at the GCI, in spring 2021.

After the disruption of the agenda, periodic (virtual) meetings between the Project Coordinator and the American partners of the project (UFMG, UNAM, MCI and GCI, represented by the National Contact Persons of Brazil, Mexico, US East, US West) took place to discuss and decide on the rescheduling of cooperation activities in the Americas.

During one of these meetings, on October 27, 2021, it was decided to hold the Pan-American Workshop on HS as a hybrid event scheduled for the end of September 2022, to be hosted jointly by the two Partners UNAM in Mexico City and UFMG in Belo Horizonte.

Unfortunately, a further resurgence of the COVID pandemic at the beginning of 2022 also made this new schedule unfeasible.

At the end of 2022, it was finally judged impossible to organize an event of such impact in the remaining timeline of the IPERION HS project, and its organization was cancelled. We are sure that E-RIHS ERIC will take over in this initiative as soon as the ERIC will be operative, as part of its international cooperation policy.

Considering that several project partners had already independent scientific contacts with China, Prof. Haida Liang (NTU) proposed, in early 2019, to open a cooperation of IPERION HS/E-RIHS with the *Alliance for Science and Heritage along the Silk Road* and to try to connect all the separate initiatives. The *Alliance* is a research infrastructure launched in 2017 with 22 member organisations across China.

We then had an exchange with Dr. Bomin Su, Director of the Conservation Research Department of the Dunhuang Academy. Dunhuang Academy is in charge of the UNESCO world heritage site of Mogao caves along the ancient Silk Road. Prof. Su was also the Principal Investigator of a project funded by the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology to develop the first mobile laboratory for archaeological excavation in China. We agreed to jointly organise a symposium hosted by the *Alliance* in 2021. The idea was to connect the *Alliance* with IPERION HS/E-RIHS to communicate how an integrated research infrastructure operates in Europe, and to showcase good practices useful for adoption/implementation in China.

Needless to say, this initiative too was frozen by the pandemic. A first attempt at rescheduling it to end of 2022/ beginning of 2023 failed as well.

Cooperation with China is, to our knowledge, in the programmes of E-RIHS ERIC. Thus, these actions are expected to regain their momentum within the ERIC international cooperation strategy.

3. Cooperation actions performed in virtual mode

As it happened with most of the other project activities, wherever possible, we tried to unblock cooperation actions by implementing them in the virtual format. The ResInfra Pilot action proved to be an exceptional means of maintaining the existing relationships with the CELAC regional hubs (ANTECIPA at UFMG in Brazil and LANCIC at UNAM in Mexico) through a very difficult period for international cooperation. Yet it even enabled further initiatives of cooperation.

In the following we list the major cooperation activities held in virtual format only:

- To remain in line with the Pan-American initiative, on October 6th, 2021, a virtual *Workshop on Transatlantic Cooperation in Heritages Science*, [2] was jointly organized with the American partners GCI, UFMG and UNAM. The three topics (Cooperation Themes) discussed were: 1. Training and Dissemination; 2. International Networking Initiatives in the Pandemic Times; 3. Opening Heritage Science Data at the Global Level. The talks given by the experts from UNAM (MX), ANTECIPA (BR), Getty Conservation Institute (US), Cyprus Institute (CY), Malta (MT), Slovenia (SI), National Gallery of London (UK) and Italy (IT) were recorded, and they are available on the E-RIHS YouTube channel [3].
- IPERION HS and the ResInfra Pilot co-organized a session and met (virtually) on the 16th RDA Plenary, originally planned in presence in Costa Rica. The Session was titled “Linguistic and

Disciplinary Barriers to Heritage Science Data Interoperability” (November 11, 2020). Heritage science and data researchers from both CELAC and EU regions discussed there some of the major obstacles to a full multi-disciplinary and multilingual interoperability of data.

- New relationships established through the participation to the ResInfra project permitted the start of a cooperation in Mexico between the UNAM and the INAH (Instituto Nacional de Antropología e Historia). A virtual meeting at a high level between UNAM, INAH and the management team of IPERION HS, mediated by the Mexican CONACYT, was organized on 2021, June 23rd. The immediate outcome for the project was the production of a programme of cooperation between INAH and E-RIHS/IPERION HS, with INAH experts engaged in training actions within the HS Academy.

Figure 1 Screenshots of the online workshop "Transatlantic cooperation in HS" (2021)

4. Cooperation actions performed in presence

The list of in-presence international cooperation actions contains only two events, and both involving Brazil, with the partner UFMG.

- The Brazilian hub was able to organise the only face-to-face event of international cooperation during the first two years of the project. In November 2021, the Project Coordinator was invited to visit UFMG in Belo Horizonte and to participate to the InterForensics2021 conference (in

Paranà), where he presented both the IPERION HS and the EU-LAC ResInfra initiatives. Important relationships were established with the forensic science community, which has many contact points with the heritage science one. A meeting with the Brazilian Group on Forensic Isotopes was also organised during the conference, on the possible interoperability of databases on materials between the two communities.

- The second in-presence event, even if it was technically in a hybrid format, was organized by UFMG jointly with IPERION HS and ResInfra in December 2022. The “International workshop on data interoperability in SEM-EDS” was held in Belo Horizonte, with the cooperation of ANTECIPA. An acknowledged data scientist and SEM expert from US, Nestor Zaluzec, gave several lectures at the workshop. The workshop was the final event of the data interoperability pilot and saw the participation of several partners of the IPERION HS project, interested in SEM-EDS data interoperability.

Figure 2 The IPERION HS coordinator during a meeting with ANTECIPA in Brazil

5. Conclusion

After the 16 international cooperation events achieved by IPERION CH, the expectations were high on prosecuting the contacts of IPERION HS/E-RIHS outside Europe. Unfortunately, the pandemic emergency started before the project itself, and disrupted all the plans of opening new partnerships and reinforcing the existing ones.

The only relationship that was spared by these events (it was actually reinforced) has been the cooperation with the Brazilian hub, the ANTECIPA consortium, also a partner of this project (UFMG). This result was achieved also thanks to the participation of IPERION HS to the E-RIHS Pilot in the ResInfra project, obtained by co-organising the Pilot activities. For both sides the Pilot action was beneficial to deepen the existing relationships, reinvigorating common plans and pointing to future initiatives of cooperation. We therefore thank the EC and the ResInfra Project Coordinator for securing us this framework for all the duration of the project, and across severely difficult times.

Of the four RIs leading pilot actions in ResInfra, E-RIHS was the only not yet in the ERIC status. During the project lifetime, E-RIHS finished its preparatory phase and entered the implementation one. The IPERION HS project, through Task 8.6 activities, was an important support to the Pilot and was key to its success.

As IPERION HS has been the last Integrating Activity project for the heritage science community, the task of leading the international cooperation is now responsibility of E-RIHS, currently in its last months of the implementation, which is expected to be an ERIC within the year. The E-RIHS international cooperation programme is currently shaped by E-RIHS IP Task 6.3, to provide a base for the ERIC policies. Then, and finally, best wishes to E-RIHS ERIC for the establishment of a global heritage science community!

References

- [1] IPERION CH Deliverable D.12.7 Report on cooperation actions and plan for pan-European Development.
- [2] <https://www.iperionhs.eu/workshop-transatlantic-cooperation-in-heritage-science-report/>
- [3] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aRRmlhZ7KYI&list=PL9cfK7AHGZ9HEO128HYTOpCTwbxRgDTME>
- [4] <https://resinfra-eulac.eu>